

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

Title: **A chromosome-scale genome assembly of the grape powdery mildew pathogen *Erysiphe necator* reveals its genomic architecture and previously unknown features of its biology.**

Running title: A chromosome-scale genome of the grape powdery mildew.

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S1. SUPPLEMENTARY RESULTS

S1.1 Obtaining a chromosome-level genome assembly for EnFRAME01. The genome of *E. necator* isolate EnFRAME01 (EnFRAME01) was sequenced with a PacBio Sequel I platform using two SMRT cells, which produced a total of 991,705 reads with an average length of 16 kb and an estimated coverage of 127x. The PacBio reads were assembled with Canu (1) into a preliminary genome assembly of 83.0 Mb containing 71 contigs with an L50 of 7. Two rounds of polishing using 40 M paired-end Illumina reads (75x coverage) performed 1,170 and 35 corrections in the assembly, respectively, indicating that further polishing would not have provided any major further improvements. A total of 135 M Illumina paired-end reads generated based on the chromatin conformation capture technique Hi-C (2) were used to merge the polished contigs into predicted chromosomes using Proximo (Phase Genomics), followed by manual adjustments using Juicebox v1.11.08 (3). The resulting and final genome assembly of EnFRAME01 contained 81.1 Mb organized into 34 scaffolds with an L50 of 5 and an N50 of 7.98 Mb (Fig 1 and Table S1). The size of the genome assembly obtained for EnFRAME01 is significantly smaller than that of C-strain, which has estimated size of 126 ± 18 Mb (4). However, k-mer counting of the Illumina reads for the C-strain predicted a genome size of 82.7 Mb, which is consistent with the genome assembly obtained in this study.

Of the 34 scaffolds, 11 represented full chromosomes, 22 remained unplaced, and one corresponded to the mitochondrial genome of the fungus, which was 99.7% similar to the mitochondrial genome of C-strain (21) (Fig S2 and Table 1). To evaluate the integrity of the EnFRAME01 genome assembly, a BUSCO analysis in genome mode (5) was next conducted, which indicated 98.2% completeness with only 0.3% duplication and 0.8% fragmentation (Table S1). Moreover, Illumina and PacBio reads were mapped to the assembly to identify collapsed regions. A total of 99.3% of the trimmed Illumina reads mapped to the assembly, and 97.4% mapped in proper pair. From the PacBio reads, 93.2% mapped to the assembly. Coverage analysis revealed only five putative collapsed regions, which were located in repeat-rich regions (>88% repetitive) of five different chromosomes and totaling 450 kb in size (Fig S3). Two of the collapsed regions co-localized with regions containing clusters of 5S and 18S-5.8S-28S rDNA, and the three others were located at or physically close to the predicted centromeres.

Next to the absence of major assembly gaps, all chromosomes were also putatively assembled telomere-to-telomere and had 22 to 31 copies of the canonical telomeric repeat 5'-TTAGGG-3' at both their ends. Centromeric regions were also predicted in all chromosomes and based on their positioning, chromosomes could be considered as metacentric, except for Chr8 which was submetacentric and Chr10 which was subtelocentric (22) (Fig S1). Moreover, centromeric regions corresponded to large segments of the chromosomes that accounted for 12.8 Mb (15.8%) of the genome and ranged in size from 0.85 Mb in Chr2 to 2.0 Mb in Chr4 (Table 1). Similar-sized centromeres were reported for the wheat powdery mildew (PM) *B. graminis* f.sp. *tritici* (9) but they are poorly conserved between the two species and both species

have overall low synteny (Fig S4). Instead, long syntenic regions were present between Chr1, Chr2, and Chr5 of *E. necator*, and chr-05, chr-08, and chr-01 of *B. graminis* f.sp. *tritici*, respectively (Fig S4). Collectively, these results indicate that centromeric regions are poorly conserved between *E. necator* and *B. graminis* f.sp. *tritici* and exhibit extensive inter-chromosomal rearrangements. Similar results were obtained by aligning the genome of *E. necator* with those of the cereal PM pathogens *B. graminis* f.sp. *tritiale* (13) and *B. graminis* f.sp. *hordei* (6).

S1.2 Genes encoding proteases in the genome of EnFRAME01. The genome of EnFRAME01 contained a total of 174 genes encoding proteases, which is at the lower end compared to other fungal genomes (7). The proteases present in the genome of EnFRAME01 could be further classified into serine ($n=51$), cysteine ($n=50$), metallo ($n=47$), threonine ($n=17$), aspartic ($n=7$), and inhibitor proteases ($n=2$) (Table S4). The protease encoded by the gene *HI914_05529* was also classified as a CAZyme, which was a serine protease predicted to belong to the CE1 acetylxylylan esterase CAZyme family. A total of 27 proteases were predicted to be secreted. Most of the secreted proteases ($n=19$) were serine proteases, followed by aspartic ($n=5$), metallo ($n=2$), and cysteine ($n=1$) proteases (Table S4).

S1.3 Secondary metabolism in EnFRAME01. The genome of EnFRAME01 contained only eight genes encoding key enzymes required for the biosynthesis of secondary metabolites, including one type I polyketide synthase (PKS), one type III PKS, three terpene synthases (TSs), one non-ribosomal peptide synthetase (NRPS), and two NRPS-like enzymes (Table S5). The single Type I PKS in *E. necator* (*HI914_06546*) had the typical domain architecture of non-reducing PKSs, and was composed of a starter unit ACP transacylase domain at its N-terminus, followed by a beta-ketoacyl synthase domain, an acyl transferase domain, a polyketide synthase dehydratase domain, and a phosphor-pantetheine attachment site at its C-terminus. Of the three TS-encoding genes in EnFRAME01, one (i.e. *HI914_04683*) encoded a squalene synthase that is homologous to the *S. cerevisiae* ERG9 (47.1% aa product identity; e-value= 2.88E-139) that catalyzes two molecules of farnesyl pyrophosphate to form squalene, one of the main steps in the sterol biosynthesis pathway (8). The other two TSs encoded by *HI914_04296* and *HI914_01229*, respectively were homologous to Al-2 (P37295; 48.8% aa product identify; e-value= 0) and Al-3 (P24322; 69.5% aa product identity; e-value= 3.46e-165) encoded by the *albino-2* and *albino-3* genes from *Neurospora crassa*, respectively. Both *albino-2* and *albino-3* genes encode key enzymes for carotenoid biosynthesis, and have been named after the albino phenotype of their mutant alleles in *N. crassa*, caused by absence of carotenoid pigments (9, 10). The NRPS-encoding gene *HI914_04002* present in EnFRAME01 was homologous to the *Fusarium graminearum* NPS2 gene (I1RN14; 34.3% aa product identity; e-value= 0) that encodes an enzyme involved in the biosynthesis of intracellular siderophore ferricrocin (11). Finally, of the two NRPS-like genes present in the genome of EnFRAME01, one (*HI914_00236*) was homologous to the *S. cerevisiae* *Lys2* (P07702; 48.2% aa product identity; e-value= 0) that encodes an L-2-aminoacidopate reductase involved in the biosynthesis of lysine from L-alpha-

aminoadipate (12). The product of the second gene (*HI914_04388*) had low homology (aa identity < 30% product aa identity) with other characterized proteins, but the putative pathways associated with them is unknown.

S1.4 Genes encoding cytochrome P450s in the genome of EnFRAME01. A total of 11 genes encoding cytochrome P450s were identified in the genome of EnFRAME01 (Table S6, and Fig S5), based on a search for the signature domain of cytochrome P450 (PF00067) among its proteins. This is again on the lower end as compared to other fungal genomes (15). Among the genes encoding cytochrome P450s in EnFRAME01 was *CYP51* (*HI914_01650*), which encodes for the sterol 14- α -demethylase enzyme in the sterol biosynthesis pathway that is the target of sterol demethylation inhibitor (DMI) fungicides. Increase in copy number of *CYP51* in *E. necator* has been associated with increase in tolerance to DMI fungicides (4). However, *CYP51* is present as a single-copy gene in the genome of EnFRAME01. The rest of the genes encoding cytochrome P450s present in EnFRAME01 were members of the *CYP52* ($n=1$), *CYP53* ($n=1$), *CYP544* ($n=1$), and *CYP617* ($n=1$) families, and six could not be classified because they lacked homology (aa product identity < 45%) to the curated fungal cytochrome P450s (<https://drnelson.uthsc.edu/P450seqs.dbs.html>). Notably, the *E. necator* *CYP52* (*HI914_06503*) is homologous to the *g430* from *Fusarium* sp. strain RK97-94 (A0A6S6AA17; 57.1% aa product identity; e-value= 0) whose product is involved in the biosynthesis of 1233A (16), an inhibitor of HMG-CoA synthase in the mevalonate pathway (17) with antibacterial and antifungal activities (18) (16). Also, the *E. necator* *CYP53* (*HI914_00178*) is homologous to the *bphA* (P17549; 56.3% aa product identity; e-value= 0) from *Aspergillus niger*, whose product is a benzoate 4-monooxygenase that converts benzoic acids, natural phenolic defense compounds produced by plants (19), into the less toxic *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid (20).

S1.5 Genes encoding transporters in the genome of EnFRAME01. In order to identify the arsenal of transporters present in EnFRAME01, the predicted proteins of EnFRAME01 were queried with BLASTp against the Transporter Classification Database (TCDB) (e-value < 1E-10). This revealed a total of 1,238 genes (16.5% of all genes) encoding putative transporters from 258 distinct families in the genome of EnFRAME01 (Table S7). Two families stood out for their high frequency, i.e. the eukaryotic nuclear pore complex (E-NPC) family ($n=125$) and the major facilitator superfamily (MFS) ($n=64$). NPCs are large proteinaceous structures that mediate bidirectional nucleocytoplasmic transport (13). MFS transporters, on the other hand, are involved in nutrient uptake, multidrug resistance, and metabolite extrusion (14), which makes them of particular importance for fungal pathogens. Most MFS transporters in EnFRAME01 are from three subfamilies, the sugar porter family ($n=19$), the Drug:H⁺ Antiporter 1 (DHA1) family ($n=16$), and the Drug:H⁺ Antiporter 2 (DHA2) family ($n=9$). The DHA1 and DHA2 families of MFS transporters are typically drug-efflux pumps associated with the extrusion of toxic compounds out of the cell. Another category of drug-efflux pumps commonly associated with antimicrobial resistance is the ATP-binding cassette (ABC) transporters. The genome of EnFRAME01 contained a total of 21 genes encoding ABC

transporters from seven subfamilies, i.e. ABCB ($n=5$), ABCF ($n=5$), ABCC ($n=4$), ABCG ($n=3$), ABCD ($n=2$), ABCE ($n=1$), and ABCI ($n=1$) (Fig S6). All 21 ABC transporters contained at least one nucleotide binding domain (NBD), which is characteristic of this family. The seven ABC transporters from subfamilies ABCF, ABCE, and ABCI lacked transmembrane domains (TMDs), and are likely involved in functions not related to transmembrane transport. All the remaining 14 ABC transporters from families ABCB, ABCC, ABCD, and ABCG, contained transmembrane domains. Of these, eight were half-length transporters, of which six had the domain topology TMD-NBD and two had the reverse topology NBD-TMD. The other six ABC transporters were full-length transporters containing two TMD domains and two NBD domains each. Of these, five had the domain topology (TMD-NBD)₂ and one had the reverse topology (NBD-TMD)₂.

S1.6 Genes encoding carbohydrate-active enzymes (CAZymes) in the genome of EnFRAME01.

The genome of EnFRAME01 contained a total of 160 genes predicted to encode CAZymes, representing 171 CAZyme modules from five major classes, i.e., glycoside hydrolases (GH), auxiliary activity (AA), glycosyl transferases (GT), carbohydrate esterases (CE), and carbohydrate-binding modules (CBM), whereas no CAZyme from the sixth major class, polysaccharide lyases (PL), was present in EnFRAME01 (Table S8). The most abundant CAZyme module was GT2 ($n=11$), followed by GH16 ($n=10$), GH18 ($n=9$), and GH76 ($n=7$). There were 11 CAZymes containing a domain architecture composed of more than one CAZyme module. Most of the CAZymes ($n=7$) contained a chitin-binding module (CBM18) combined either with a GH18 chitinase domain ($n=3$), an AA5 copper radical oxidase domain ($n=2$), a GH16 β -1,3-glucanase domain ($n=1$), or a CE4 acetylxyylan esterase domain ($n=1$). The other four multi-module CAZymes included a putative glycoamylase with a starch-binding domain (GH15+CBM20), a putative 1,4-alpha-glucan-branching enzyme with a glycogen-binding domain (GH13+CBM48), a putative β -1,3-glucanosyltransglycosylase with a β -1,3-glucan-binding domain (GH72+CBM43), and a gene similar to N-acetylglactosamine deacetylase with an α -1,4-N-acetylglactosamine-binding domain (CE18+CBM87). A total of 60 CAZymes were predicted to be secreted, which included seven from the AA class, seven from the CE class, 43 from the GH class, and three from the GT class. Among the 60 secreted CAZymes, 12 were predicted to act on plant cell walls, including hemicellulose ($n=9$), cellulose ($n=2$), and pectin ($n=1$) (6) (Table S8).

S1.7 Genes encoding candidate secreted effector proteins (CSEPs) in the genome of EnFRAME01.

Typical criteria used to classify proteins as CSEPs in PMs include the presence of a signal peptide (SP), no transmembrane domains (TMDs), and no homology to proteins outside the Erysiphales (21). However, these criteria might underestimate the true number of CSEPs in PMs. For example, the barley PM CSEP BEC1019 (AHZ59730.1) is a metalloprotease (22) with homologs in several non-PM pathogens, including *Botrytis spp.* and *Fusarium spp.* To overcome such drawbacks in the classification of secreted proteins (SPs) as CSEPs in *E. necator*, we used three lines of evidence, i.e. i) the lack of homology to proteins outside Erysiphales, ii) their classification as candidate effectors based on the

EffectorP software (23), and iii) their domain and amino acid composition (i.e. having a SP and being shorter than 250 aa, being cysteine-rich, having no TMDs and no GPI-anchor). Among the 527 SPs predicted in EnFRAME01 ([Table S9](#)), 152 could be classified as CSEPs based on lack of homology to proteins from non-Eurotiomycetes, 151 based on EffectorP classification, and 120 based on their domain composition. The union of these three sets that satisfied all of our parameters for classifying SPs as CSEPs, yielded a total of 234 CSEPs in *E. necator* ([Fig S20](#) and [Table S10](#)). As expected, this number is significantly larger than the 150 CSEPs reported for the *E. necator* isolate C-strain (4), but still considerably lower than the 844 CSEPs reported for the cereal PM *B. graminis* f.sp. *tritici* (24). Also, all 234 CSEP-encoding genes could be mapped to the genome of the five *E. necator* isolates sequenced before (4), although five of them were pseudogenised in one or more *E. necator* isolates by the introduction of a premature stop codon in their sequence ([Table S10](#)).

Homology searches in the NCBI nr database showed that of the 234 CSEPs predicted in EnFRAME01, 49 were species-specific and 183 had homologs in other fungi, including PM fungi ($n=183$) and/or non-PM fungi ($n=86$) ([Fig S7](#)). The majority of CSEPs shared with other PMs had homologs only in dicot-infecting PMs ($n=77$) or both in dicot and monocot-infecting PMs ($n=105$), as compared to having homologs only in monocot-infecting PMs ($n=1$) ([Table S10](#)). Twenty-four of the CSEPs also had a homolog in the Pathogen Host Interaction (PHI) database (e-value < 1E-5), of which 17 had a match to BEC1019 from *B. graminis*, GAS1 from *Magnaporthe oryzae*, Mras7 from *Metarhizium robertsii*, bim1 from *Cryptococcus neoformans*, cypB from *Beauveria bassiana*, and PBC1 from *Pyrenopeziza brassicae*, for which mutants exhibited reduced pathogenicity ([Table S10](#)).

Further sequence analysis of the EnFRAME01 CSEPs showed that of the 234 CSEPs, 38 had a conserved domain in their sequence, including a microbial-type ribonuclease (cl00212) domain ([Table S10](#)). Ribonuclease-like effectors belong to a large family of catalytically inactive RNases in cereal PMs that are generally referred to as RNase-like proteins associated with haustoria (RALPHs) (36–38). A genome-wide search for RALPHs in EnFRAME01 identified a total of 38 genes encoding RALPH-like proteins. Of the 38 RALPH-like proteins, 24 fulfilled the criteria used to classify secreted proteins as CSEPs and could thus be further considered as RALPH-like CSEPs ([Table S14](#)). A phylogenetic analysis showed that the 38 RALPH-like proteins could be organized into two clades ([Fig S9](#)). One of the clades consisted of 22 long RALPH-like proteins of 405-636 aa in size and their encoding genes mostly clustered towards the end of Chr8 ($n=13$) and Chr11 ($n=4$). The other clade contained 16 short RALPH-like proteins of 172-219 aa in size and their encoding genes mostly clustered at an 85 kb region of Chr7 ($n=10$) ([Fig S9](#)). Other domains most commonly found in the *E. necator* CSEPs were an Egh16-like virulence factor domain (PF11327) ($n=4$) and a P24 protein family domain (PF01105) ($n=4$). Phylogenetic analysis of the 11 Egh16-like proteins showed that they too formed two major clades, with one clade containing six Egh16-like proteins that were highly similar to the gEgh16 of *B. graminis* f.sp. *hordei* (34) and whose encoding genes mostly clustered in Chr4 ($n=5$). The other clade contained five Egh16-like proteins that were highly

similar to the Egh16H1 of *B. graminis* f.sp. *hordei* (35) and their encoding genes clustered in Chr2 ([Fig S10](#) and [Table S15](#)).

It is often the case that genes encoding fungal effector proteins are located in dynamic parts of the chromosomes such as sub-telomeric regions (27, 28). Analysis of the localization of the 234 CSEP-encoding genes on the 11 chromosomes of *E. necator* showed that although some genes encoding RALPH-like CSEPs ($n=6$) were located within 500 kb of the end of chromosomes Chr8, Chr10, or Chr11 ([Fig S9](#)), there was no enrichment of genes encoding CSEPs in sub-telomeric regions (i.e. no CSEP-encoding gene within 50 kb of chromosome ends), as has been observed in other fungi (27, 28), and all were totally absent from centromeric regions ([Fig 1](#)).

S1.8 “Missing ascomycete pathogen core genes” (MACGs) in the genome of EnFRAME01. To understand the molecular basis of obligate biotrophy in *E. necator*, the 181 distinct core genes that were not present in the genome of EnFRAME01 but conserved in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and other non-obligate fungi were further analyzed ([Table S11](#)). These 181 core missing genes included 95 of the 99 MACGs that were previously reported as being absent in PMs, but present in other ascomycetes ([Table S12](#)). Of the remaining four MACGs, two are likely pseudogenes in *S. cerevisiae* S288c and two, namely *HEM4* (*HI914_06207*) encoding a uroporphyrinogen-III synthase that is involved in methionine metabolism and (siro-) heme biosynthesis and *ADH4* (*HI914_02737*) encoding an alcohol dehydrogenase 4 that is involved in alcohol metabolism, were present in EnFRAME01. Of these two MACGs, *HEM4* was also present in the pea PM *Erysiphe pisi* (29), indicating that its presence in EnFRAME01 is not unique.

In accordance with previous reports that PMs lack biosynthesis of glycerol from glycolytic intermediates and biosynthesis of thiamine (21, 30), we observed the absence of a gene encoding glycerol 3-phosphatase (EC:3.1.3.21) that is required for glycerol biosynthesis in *S. cerevisiae* (31), and the absence of six genes involved in thiamine biosynthesis, namely hydroxymethylpyrimidine/phosphomethylpyrimidine kinase *THI20* (EC:2.7.1.49), 4-amino-5-hydroxymethyl-2-methylpyrimidine phosphate synthase *THI11*, repressible alkaline phosphatase *PHO8* (EC:3.1.3.1), thiamine biosynthetic bifunctional enzyme *THI6* (EC:2.5.1.3), thiamine thiazole synthase *THI4* (EC:2.4.2.60), and low molecular weight phosphotyrosine protein phosphatase *LTP1* (EC:3.1.3.48) ([Table S13](#)). In terms of nitrogen metabolism, EnFRAME01 lacked transporters from the nitrate/nitrite porter (NNP) family (TCDB family ID 2.A.1.8) as well as a nitrite reductase (EC:1.7.1.4), a nitrate reductase (EC:1.7.1.3), and a NADP-specific glutamate dehydrogenase (EC:1.4.1.4) ([Table S13](#)). A reduced arsenal of genes involved in amino acid biosynthesis was observed too, as EnFRAME01 lacked the *CAR1* (EC:3.5.3.1), *GDH1* (EC:1.4.1.4), and *GDH3* (EC:1.4.1.4) genes involved in arginine biosynthesis as well as the *ARO8* gene that encodes a general aromatic amino acid transaminase (EC:2.6.1.57 2.6.1.39 2.6.1.27 2.6.1.5) involved in phenylalanine, tyrosine, tryptophan and lysine biosynthesis ([Table S13](#)). Significant losses were also observed in genes involved in metabolism of several amino acids, including tryptophan, arginine,

proline, tyrosine, alanine, aspartate, glutamate, phenylalanine, glycine, serine, threonine, cysteine, and methionine ([Table S13](#)). Nucleotide metabolism was also impacted by gene losses, including of genes encoding guanine deaminase (EC:3.5.4.3), cytosine deaminase (EC:3.5.4.1), cytidine deaminase (EC:3.5.4.5), and uridine nucleosidase (EC:3.2.2.3). A considerable reduction in genes involved in sulfur metabolism was also observed. Specifically, the *MET3*, *MET10*, *MET14*, and *MET16* genes that are part of the sulfate assimilation pathway and collectively synthesize sulfite from sulfate were absent in *E. necator*. Lastly, a reduction in genes for sterol biosynthesis was observed as well. Specifically, *E. necator* lacked genes encoding sterol O-acyltransferase (EC:2.3.1.26), and the genes *ERG4* (EC:1.3.1.71) and *ERG5* (EC:1.14.19.41) that are required for ergosterol biosynthesis in yeast and other fungi (32) ([Table S13](#)).

S1.9 Analysis of repetitive DNA. A *de novo* annotation of repetitive DNA revealed that 62.7% (50.8 Mb) of the EnFRAME01 genome was composed of transposable elements (TEs), which is in agreement with the previous estimate of $62.9 \pm 3\%$ for C-strain (7). The abundant presence of TEs in the genome of *E. necator* suggests that genome defense mechanisms against TE activity are inactive in this species. Indeed, a tBLASTn search (e-value < $1E^{-3}$) for homologs of the *RID1* (XP_011392925.1), *Dim-2* (XP_959891.1), *MASC1* (AAC49849.1), and *MASC2* (AAC03766.1) genes that mediate RIP and MIP (Methylation Induced Premeiotically) in fungi (46) showed that these are absent from the genome of *E. necator*, indicating that RIP and MIP have likely no effect on TE activity or diversification of their nucleotide sequences. Even so, an examination of the nucleotide divergence of TEs in EnFRAME01 exhibited bimodal distribution with two peaks, at approximately 5% and 21% of divergence, respectively ([Fig 2B](#)). The first peak at ~5% divergence was dominated by LTRs (1.2 Mb, 35.5%), RC (1.0 Mb, 30.7%), and unknown elements (0.8 Mb, 30.0%), whereas the second peak at ~21% divergence was dominated by LTRs (0.8 Mb, 46.2%) and the non-LTR long interspersed nuclear elements (LINEs; 0.8 Mb, 43.7%) ([Fig 2B](#)). This bimodal distribution contrasts the pattern reported previously in *B. graminis* f.sp. *hordeii*, for which a single recent burst of TE proliferation was proposed (33). However, our analysis of the genomic data of different *B. graminis* formae speciales (24, 34) also revealed bimodal distributions of TE divergence in these genomes.

S1.10 Distribution of genes and repeats on the chromosomes of EnFRAME01. An examination of the distribution of repeats and protein coding genes on the 11 chromosomes of EnFRAME01 showed large differences in gene density among the chromosomes ([Fig 1](#)). Specifically, gene density was highest in Chr2 (107 genes per Mb) and lowest in Chr8 (63 genes per Mb), with an overall average of 88 genes per Mb for the entire genome. Likewise, the density of repetitive DNA also differed among the chromosomes and was highest in Chr8 (70.0%) and lowest in Chr2 (55.6%). Although no major differences in TE content within the flanking regions of genes encoding CAZymes, proteases, CSEPs, and non-CSEP secreted proteins was observed, intergenic regions of CSEP genes were significantly

longer and richer in repetitive DNA (Fig 3A to 3B, and Table S17). For instance, while intergenic regions of CSEP-coding genes averaged 11.4 kb in size and 48.6% in repeat content, intergenic regions of BUSCO genes averaged 6.1 kb in size and 31.7% in repeat content. Moreover, intergenic regions downstream of CSEP-encoding genes had the highest content of LTR retrotransposons and RC DNA transposons as compared to genes from the above four functional categories (Fig S13). This indicates that TEs were essentially evenly distributed in gene-flanking regions, but small differences in TE content could be observed in the vicinity of CSEP-encoding genes. Overall, these results indicate that the genome of *E. necator* exhibits local instead of large-scale compartmentalization.

S1.11 Gene duplications. The absence of RIP in *E. necator* suggests that, similar to TEs, duplicated genes could also be retained at a higher rate within the genome of the fungus, as compared to other ascomycete fungi. A large number of 941 gene duplicates were identified in the genome of *E. necator* by self-BLASTp search, while an enrichment analysis further showed that different functional gene categories exhibiting different rates and modes of gene duplication (Fig 4A and Table S18). This was most evident in CSEPs, which experienced higher rates of gene duplications and, in contrast to other functional gene categories, almost equal levels of dispersed, proximal, and tandem gene duplications (Fig 4A).

An examination of the nucleotide divergence among copies of genes with different duplication modes showed that dispersed gene duplicates (DGDs) had significantly higher levels of nucleotide divergence (median=65.6%), as compared to proximal gene duplicates (PGDs; median=90.1%) (p -value=1.55E-13) and tandem gene duplicates (TGDs; median=93.4%) (p -value=9.26E-14), which did not statistically differ from each other (p -value=0.46) (Fig 4C). This indicates that gene copies physically close in the genome of *E. necator* are more conserved and thus more likely to contribute to genetic redundancy than dispersed copies that are likely to contribute more to functional diversification. Alternatively, by considering nucleotide sequence similarity as a proxy for the age of gene duplication events (36, 37), these results suggest that copies of recently duplicated genes of EnFRAME01 were more likely to be physically close in the genome than older duplications. To assess the age of the duplication events, we examined the rate of synonymous substitutions per synonymous site (K_S) among the gene duplicates in the different categories of gene duplication modes. We also examined the rates of nonsynonymous (K_A) to synonymous nucleotide substitutions (K_A/K_S) in order to evaluate differences in selection pressure among them (38). The distribution of K_S and K_A/K_S values differed among genes with different duplication modes, with TGDs and PGDs experiencing significantly lower median K_S values and higher median K_A/K_S values than DGDs (Fig 4D and Fig S16A), suggesting that they are more recent duplicates and under more relaxed selection pressure. However, DGDs showed a distinctive bimodal distribution of K_S values with one peak at $K_S \approx 3$ -3.5 and a second peak at $K_S \approx 0.05$, suggesting that a substantial number of DGDs were younger in age and were generated by recent gene duplication events (Fig 4C and Fig S16A). A similar observation was made when plotting the frequency of the K_S estimates obtained for each gene duplication pair, in which

case the K_S distribution did not follow the expected exponential decrease in frequency with the age of the duplicates (38) but instead, a secondary peak was observed at the tail of the distribution at $K_S \approx 3$ (Fig S16B). This suggested that at least two bursts of large gene duplication events took place in the evolutionary history of *E. necator* (37, 39, 40). Finally, when examining nucleotide divergence among gene copies in each functional gene category, the CSEP-encoding genes again differed markedly from the other gene functional categories as they exhibited significantly lower median K_S values and higher median K_A/K_S values (Fig S16C), suggesting that CSEP gene duplicates were mostly younger in age and evolved faster as compared to other gene categories. Taken together, these results suggest that gene duplication contributes to genome plasticity in *E. necator* but differentially affects different functional gene categories, including their rate of duplication, mode of evolution, and organization of their paralogs in the genome.

S1.12 Genes and regions with copy number variations (CNVs) among isolates of *E. necator*. In

order to identify regions with CNVs, whole-genome sequencing reads of *E. necator* isolates Branching, C-strain, e1-101, Lodi, and Ranch9 (4) were mapped to the genome assembly of EnFRAME01, and CNV regions were subsequently identified based on differences in coverage depth. A total of 1,760 CNV regions were identified, covering 5.5 Mb (6.9%) of the EnFRAME01 genome (Fig S17 and Table S20). Regions with CNV were fairly dispersed throughout the 11 chromosomes of EnFRAME01 but mostly overlapped with predicted TEs. Interestingly, while 7.5% of the total deleted regions overlapped with RC elements, only 1.2% of the duplicated regions were associated with RCs (Fig S17C), indicating a differential loss and acquisition by duplication of RC elements among the strains.

When considering genes only with CNVs, then these were most likely to be affected by duplications rather than deletions. Indeed, a total of 122 CNV genes were identified among the five isolates analyzed (Table S21), which is slightly less than the 135 CNV genes reported previously among the same five isolates (4). However, among the 122 CNV genes identified, 66 were absent in the previous reference genome annotation of *E. necator* isolate C-strain. Moreover, from the 135 CNV genes previously reported using the genome of C-strain as reference, 75 were absent in the genome annotation of EnFRAME01, with the majority of them ($n=60$) mapping to highly repetitive regions (>90%). This suggests that the previous CNV analysis (4) missed several CNV genes and reported many transposon-like CNV genes. Of the 122 CNV genes, only 37 had a neighboring CNV gene, indicating that CNV regions typically affected single genes instead of groups of genes. From the 122 CNV genes identified, 14 formed two large clusters of consecutive CNV genes. The largest of these clusters contained eight consecutive genes located within a 22.2 kb region of Chr2, all of which had two copies in isolate Ranch9. Among them, *HI914_01688* is predicted to encode a diacylglycerol O-acyltransferase (DGAT) that catalyzes the last step in triacylglycerol (TGA) synthesis from diacylglycerol and fatty acyl-CoA as substrates, *HI914_01692* encodes a putative zinc finger C2H2 transcription factor homologous to *crzA* that plays a role in proper chitin and glycan incorporation into the cell wall, and *HI914_01695* is predicted to encode an alternative oxidase (AOX) that

participates in the electron transfer chain (ETC) by providing an alternative route for electrons. The other cluster of CNV genes contained six consecutive genes located within a 11.4 kb region of Chr10 and had five copies in isolate C-strain, four copies in isolates Ranch9 and e1-101, and three copies in isolate Lodi ([Table S21](#)). Among these six genes, *HI914_07035* showed homology to the yeast *RRP8* gene (P38961) that encodes an rDNA methyltransferase responsible for the N1-methylation of adenine 645 of 25S rRNA, *HI914_07036* showed homology to the yeast *RPB5* (P20434) gene that encodes the subunit RPB5 of the DNA-directed RNA polymerases I, II, and III, *HI914_07038* encoded a putative mitochondrial GTPase, and *HI914_07039* encoded a secreted protein containing an ankyrin repeat domain (PF12796). The rest 48 CNV genes formed 19 smaller clusters containing two to four genes, whereas 60 CNV genes were not clustered, i.e. there were no genes with CNV within the next 10 genes up- and downstream. This indicates that duplicated segments in the genome of EnFRAME01 are typically short and affect only one or a few genes at a time, instead of long segmental duplications that could affect several genes at once.

S1.13 A putative PM-specific carboxylesterase varying in copy number. An inspection of the 122 genes with CNVs among the isolates of *E. necator* showed that gene *HI914_00624* was the one exhibiting the most dynamic changes in copy numbers. Predicted copy numbers of this gene ranged from one in isolate EnFRAME01, two in isolates Ranch9 and e1-101, 13 in isolate Branching, 20 in isolate C-strain, and 31 in isolate Lodi. Functional annotations of *HI914_00624* using InterProScan showed that it encodes a predicted secreted carboxylesterase (CE). CEs (E.C. 3.1.1.1) form a large multimember family of ubiquitous enzymes that play crucial roles in endo- and xenobiotic metabolism (42–44). Not surprisingly, a search for homologues of *HI914_00624* in the NCBI nr database showed that these were abundantly present in both within PM and non-PM fungi ([Fig 5B](#)). However, the phylogenetic tree constructed using the top 400 best blastp hits in the NCBI nr database (2022-06-20), representing at least 195 distinct fungal species, showed that *HI914_00624* belonged to a distinct phylogenetic clade that included 22 CEs from only PM species ([Fig 5C](#)). The monocot-infecting PMs *B. graminis* f.sp. *hordeij*, *B. graminis* f.sp. *tritici*, and *B. graminis* f.sp. *triticales* each had only a single homolog of *HI914_00624* from this clade. In contrast, the dicot-infecting PMs *Erysiphe neolycopersici*, *Erysiphe pulchra*, *Golovinomyces cichoracearum*, and *Golovinomyces magnicellulatus*, had multiple homologs of *HI914_00624* ([Table S23](#)). This indicates that duplication of *HI914_00624* occurs more frequently in dicot-infecting than monocot-infecting PMs. To further explore the characteristics of this novel PM-specific clade of CEs, we searched for the Ser-Asp/Glu-His catalytic triad that is indispensable to the function of CEs as well as for the consensus Gly-x-Ser-x-Gly pentapeptide motif within which the Ser heading the catalytic triad residue is generally fixed in CEs (45, 46). A multiple sequence alignment of the 22 CEs included in the *HI914_00624* clade showed that these two motifs were poorly conserved in *HI914_00624* and its homologs ([Fig S20](#) and [Table S23](#)). Collectively, these results suggest that *HI914_00624* is a member of new clade of potentially non-catalytically active CEs (47) that experience dynamic CNV in dicot-infecting PMs.

S2. SUPPLEMENTARY METHODS

S2.1 Fungal isolate, nucleic acid extraction and sequencing. The sequenced *E. necator* isolate EnFRAME01 is sensitive to FRAC (Fungicide Resistance Action Committee) group 3, 7, 11, 13, 50, and U6 fungicides. To obtain high-molecular weight (HMW) DNA, EnFRAME01 was propagated on *Vitis vinifera* L., cv. 'Chardonnay' seedlings grown in a custom Percival biocontainment growth chamber (Percival Scientific, Perry, IA) at 22°C with a 16 h photoperiod. Briefly, conidia were harvested from infected grape leaves 7 to 10 days after inoculation and again every 5 to 7 days for 30 days. A vacuum (Shop-Vac model 2030100, Williamsport, PA) reduced from 18mm to 8mm ID hose with a Whatman #1 filter paper (Whatman International Ltd., Maidstone, England) placed in-line at the reducer (resulting 11t m/sec flowrate) was used to collect conidia from leaves. The collected conidia were immediately suspended in 0.05% Tween 20 (Sigma-Aldrich, Saint Louis, MO) in nuclease-free water, and passed through a 70 μ m cell strainer (Fisher Scientific, Pittsburgh, PA) to remove debris. The conidial suspension was then centrifuged for 5 min at 4696 x g at 4°C, the supernatant was poured off, and the pellet flash-frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C. For DNA extraction, the ball milling step was omitted and no more than 100 mg of the conidia were combined with 700 μ L of pre-warmed 65°C lysis buffer and 300 μ L 65°C 5% (w/v) Sarcosyl as in Feehan et al. (2017) (48), followed by a 40 min incubation at 65°C. The chloroform:isoamyl alcohol (24:1) DNA extraction step was performed as in Feehan et al. (2017) (48) but the isopropanol precipitation step was incubated for 10 min at room temperature and the resulting pellet was dissolved in 300 μ L pH 8.0 TE buffer by incubating for 20 min at 37°C. Removal of RNA was accomplished by the addition of 1.5 μ L RNase A (100 mg/ml, Qiagen, Germantown, MD) to each 300 μ L and incubated for 2 hr at 37°C. Phenol:chloroform:isoamyl alcohol (25:24:1) extractions were performed in 5PRIME Phase Lock Heavy Gel tubes (Quantabio, Beverly, MA) and the tubes were centrifuged for 5 min at 12,000 x g at room temperature following the Phase Lock protocol. The DNA was precipitated as in Feehan et al. (2017) (48) with the addition of three extra -20°C 70% ethanol washes of the DNA pellets followed by air drying at room temperature in a laminar flow hood. The DNA pellets were resuspended in 50 μ L 10 mM pH8.0 Tris-HCL and allowed to dissolve for 30 min at room temperature and stored at 4°C. All DNA transfer steps were done using wide-bore low-retention nuclease-free filter pipet tips. The quality and quantity of DNA was initially assessed using a NanoDrop 2000C spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA) and Qubit 2.0 fluorometer using the dsDNA High Sensitivity kit (Invitrogen/Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA) and 20 μ L (~100 ng) of DNA was run on a 0.7% agarose gel at 90V for 1 hr.

Total RNA was isolated from conidia of EnFRAME01. Briefly, for each isolate, grape leaves with actively growing colonies were held above a 6" x 6" sterile glass slide and gently flicked to dislodge and spread the conidia into a semi-confluent monolayer on the slide. Conidia were incubated in a sealed chamber with a water reservoir for 8 hours, after which the conidia were removed with a razor blade and immediately transferred to Eppendorf tubes and snap frozen in liquid nitrogen. Assessment of the samples' quality was

carried out on Qubit and Agilent 2100 analysers, and 250-300 bp cDNA libraries were constructed and sequenced on Illumina NovaSeq6000 platform, after which the raw sequencing data were filtered to remove low-quality reads and adapter sequences. A minimum of 157,294,292 clean reads were produced from each RNA sample, all with Q30 values of 95% or higher.

S2.2 Genome assembly. Canu v1.8 (1) was used to assemble PacBio reads with parameters genomeSize=90m corOutCoverage=60 minReadLength=5000 minOverlapLength=3000 corMinCoverage=5 corMhapSensitivity=normal correctedErrorRate=0.03. To predict chromosomes based on chromatin conformation capture, Hi-C reads were mapped to the assembly with BWA-MEM v0.7.17 (49) with parameters -5 -S , which allow the mapping of each read end individually. The mapped Hi-C reads were processed with samblaster v0.1.24 (50) to mark PCR duplicates, and with SAMtools v1.9 (51) to remove reads with one of the ends unmapped and to remove -Psupplementary alignments (SAM flag = 2216). The resulting mapped Hi-C reads were used to generate links with the *matlock* script (<https://github.com/phasegenomics/matlock>). Links were then sorted by the mapping position of the left end, and then by the mapping position of the right end. The assembled contigs were used to generate an assembly file with the scripts *makeAgpFromFasta.py* and *agp2assembly.py* (https://github.com/phasegenomics/juicebox_scripts). Finally, the assembly file and the sorted links were used by the script *run-assembly-visualizer.sh* from the 3D-DNA package (52) to produce a hic file, which was visualized and edited with Juicebox v1.11.08 (3). Based on Hi-C interaction frequency visualized with Juicebox, contigs were grouped into putative chromosomes. To evaluate the assembly integrity, the genome assembly completeness was estimated with BUSCO v5.2.1 in genome mode using as reference the fungi_odb10 database ($n=758$ BUSCO genes). Moreover, the WGS Illumina and PacBio reads were mapped to the genome assembly with BWA-MEM v0.7.17-r1188 (49) and minimap2 v2.17-r941 (53). Read coverage across the chromosomes was calculated with mosdepth v0.3.2 (54) using a sliding window of 50 kb. Windows with more than 2x the median coverage of the entire genome were considered collapsed regions. Circular representation of the chromosomes was generated with circos v0.69-8 (55). Because the resulting genome assembly (81.1 Mb) was considerably smaller than the previous estimate of 126 ± 18 Mb (4), the genome size was estimated based on the WGS Illumina reads. First, reads matching the mitochondrial genome were removed with the script *bbduk.sh* script from BBmap v38.90 using k-mer value of 29 ($k=29$). Then, genome size was estimated using the script *kmercountexact.sh* from BBmap v38.90 with parameters $k=29$ and *peaks=out_peaks.txt*.

S2.3 Gene predictions. RNA-seq reads were mapped to the genome assembly with HISAT2 v2.2.0 (56) with parameters *--max-intronlen 3000 --dta*. Transcripts were reconstructed with Trinity v2.9.1 (57) in genome-guided mode with the parameter *--jaccard_clip*, and with Stringtie v2.1.1 (58). Assembled transcripts were processed with the script *dedupe.sh* from BBMap v38-72 to remove identical or fully contained transcripts. Transcripts were mapped to the genome assembly with GMAP v2019-09-12 (59)

with parameters `--min-intronlength=20 --intronlength=3000 --format=gff3_gene` to obtain location of introns to support training of the gene predictor GeneMark-ES as described below.

Initially, gene models were generated to train *ab initio* gene predictors. Gene models were generated with GeMoMa v1.6.3 (60) using the mapped RNA-seq reads in BAM format and protein sequences from *Oidium neolycopersici* (61). Briefly, GeMoMa maps the protein sequences to a reference genome and uses RNA-seq reads to call gene models with accurate exons and introns. Gene models were filtered with GeMoMa with parameters `tpc=1 tie=1`, and putative duplicated genes were removed by identifying highly similar proteins with `cd-hit v4.7` (62) at the identity threshold of 80%, resulting in 4,279 gene models. These gene models and location of introns identified with GMAP were used to train GeneMark-ES v.4.57 (63) with parameters `--fungus --training --soft_mask auto`. Gene models were converted to ZFF format with the script `gff3_to_zff.pl` that is incorporated in the SNAP v2013-11-29 software (64). The gene models in ZFF format were filtered with the script `fathom` that is incorporated in SNAP. The scripts `forge` and `hmm-assembler.pl` were then used to train SNAP. The same gene models used to train GeneMark were used to train the Augustus v3.2.3 software (65). To reduce computational time, 1,626 models were randomly selected from the total 4,279. An initial training was performed with the script `etraining` that is incorporated in Augustus. The 1,626 models were randomly split into 1,326 models for parameter optimization and 300 models for benchmarking. After parameter optimization, sensitivity and specificity were equal to 0.838 and 0.823 at the exon level, and 0.700 and 0.667 at the gene level, respectively.

As an additional line of gene evidence, more gene models were generated with GeMoMa, using the mapped RNA-seq reads and protein sequences from *E. necator* isolate C-strain (4). Finally, Maker v2.31.10 (66) was used to generate gene models for EnFRAME01. To do so, Maker used i) the trained *ab initio* predictors GeneMark-ES, SNAP, and Augustus, ii) the gene models generated with GeMoMa, iii) the assembled transcripts, iv) protein sequences from *Blumeria graminis* f.sp. *hordei* isolate DH14 (GCA_000151065.2), *O. neolycopersici* isolate UMSG2 (GCA_003610855.1), and *Botrytis cinerea* isolate B05.10 (GCF_000143535.2), and v) the location of repetitive regions in GFF format identified with RepeatMasker. Predicted genes entirely contained within repetitive regions were further verified and removed if the encoded proteins are hypothetical or contained conserved domains typically associated with transposable elements (67). Completeness of gene prediction was estimated with BUSCO v5.2.1 in proteome mode using as reference the `fungi_odb10` database ($n = 758$ BUSCO genes).

S2.4 Characterization of repeats and of transposable elements (TEs). *De novo* TE libraries were generated for the genomes of EnFRAME01, *Blumeria graminis* f.sp. *hordei* isolate DH14 (33), *Blumeria graminis* f.sp. *tritici* isolate v3.16 (24), and *B. graminis* f.sp. *triticales* isolate THUN12 (34) using RepeatModeler v2.0.2a (68). RepeatModeler was configured to use RECON v1.08 (69) and RepeatScout v1.0.6 (70), and was executed with the parameter `-LTRStruct` to run the LTR structural discovery pipeline using `LTR_retriever v2.9.0` (71) and `LTRharvest` (72) that is part of the GenomeTools suite v1.6.2. To classify

predicted TE families, RepeatModeler used rmbblast v2.11.0+ as the search engine against known TE families in the Dfam database release 3.5 (October 2021) (73). The custom *de novo* TE libraries were then used to mask the genomes with RepeatMasker 4.1.2-p1 with parameters -xsmall -gff -s -a and using rmbblast v2.11.0+ as the search engine. The output alignment files generated by RepeatMasker were parsed with the script parseRM.pl v5.8.2 (<https://github.com/4ureliek/Parsing-RepeatMasker-Outputs>) with parameters --land 50,1 --parse --fa --nrem to estimate the abundance (bp) of each TE superfamily, to generate TE divergence landscape, and to estimated divergence of each TE family.

To estimate differences of TE divergence across the chromosomes of EnFRAME01, the GFF file produced by RepeatMasker was parsed with the script genomcov from BEDtools v2.29 (41) to find genomic regions masked more than one time, i.e., overlapping TE regions. These regions were subsequently removed from the TE annotations with the subtract script from BEDtools. Non-overlapping windows of 50 kb along the 11 chromosomes of EnFRAME01 were generated with the script makewindows from BEDtools. TE families overlapping each window and their abundances were extracted with the script intersect from BEDtools. To estimate overall divergence of TEs within each window, the divergence of TE families overlapping each window were obtained, as previously estimated with the script parseRM.pl.

For each TE family f overlapping window w , the normalized divergence $d(w)$ of TEs in the window w was estimated as $\sum_{i=0}^n \frac{d(f_i) \cdot abund(f_{iw})}{\sum_{k=1}^n abund(f_{kw})}$, where n is the total number of unique TE families that overlap the window w , $d(f_i)$ is the divergence of the TE family f_i across the entire genome, and $abund(f_{iw})$ is the total number of bases masked in w by the TE family f_i . In other words, the divergence of the TE families are multiplied by their respective abundances in the window, then divided by the total number of masked bases in the window.

S2.5 Homology-based functional annotation of predicted genes. The predicted protein sequences were queried with BLASTp against the UniProt/SwissProt database (e-value < 1E-10) and conserved PFAM domains were identified with InterProScan v5.32-71.0 (74). The outputs of BLASTp and InterProScan were processed with ANNIE (<http://genomeannotation.github.io/annie/>) to generate a 3-column table with functional descriptions, which was then used by GAG (<https://genomeannotation.github.io/GAG/>) to assign functional descriptions and conserved domains to the predicted genes, and to generate a feature table file (.tbl). The feature table file was parsed with the script tbl2asn (https://ftp.ncbi.nih.gov/toolbox/ncbi_tools/converters/by_program/tbl2asn/) to validate gene models, to generate a sequin file (.sqn) ready for submission to NCBI, and to generate a GenBank format (.gb) file.

The generated GenBank file was uploaded to antiSMASH fungal version v5.1.2 webserver to predict genes encoding key enzymes for secondary metabolism. The predicted secondary metabolite genes were queried with BLASTp (e-value < 1E-10) against the Minimum Information about a Biosynthetic Gene cluster (MIBiG) database v2 to search for homologous genes.

Genes encoding carbohydrate-active enzymes (CAZymes) were predicted with the dbCAN2 web server (75) using the HMM database v9 and three tools: HMMER (e-value < 1E-15, coverage > 0.35), DIAMOND (e-value < 1E-102), and Hotpep (Frequency > 2.6, Hits > 6). Following the dbCAN's manual, CAZymes predicted by only one tool were discarded to reduce the number of false positives. Proteases were identified by querying all the proteins against the MEROPS database v12.1 (76) with BLASTp (e-value < 1E-10), and classified based on the most homologous sequence (i.e. top BLASTp hit).

Genes encoding transporters were identified by querying the proteins against the Transporter Classification Database (TCDB) version of 2020-07-12 (77) with BLASTp (e-value < 1E-10), and classified based on the most homologous sequence. The ATP-binding cassette (ABC) transporters and the major facilitator superfamily (MFS) were further classified. ABC transporters (TCDB ID: 3.A.1) were classified into ABCB, ABCC, ABCD, ABCE, ABCF, and ABCI families based on their respective top BLASTp hits against the TCDB or based on their domain architecture (78). A maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree of the ABC transporters was inferred by aligning the protein sequences with MAFFT v7.475 (parameters: --maxiterate 1000 --localpair). All positions in the alignment containing gaps were removed with trimAl v1.4.1. A tree was then constructed with IQTREE v2.1.2 using ModelFinder to determine the best substitution model (best-fit model LG+I+G4) and to perform 1000 rapid bootstrap replicates (parameters: -m MFP -B 1000). For better visualization, the tree was rooted at the ABCI-type transporter HI914_00568. Domains were identified with a batch search (e-value < 1E-3) against the PFAM domain data base (<http://pfam.xfam.org>). Transmembrane domains were predicted with TMHMM v2.0 (<http://www.cbs.dtu.dk/services/TMHMM/>). The MFS transporters were further classified into subfamilies based on their top BLASTp hit against the TCDB database.

Genes encoding cytochrome P450s were identified by querying the predicted proteins with the script `hmmsearch` from HMMER v3.3.2 with maximum e-value of 0.001 (parameters: -E 0.001) using the HMM model for cytochrome P450 (PF00067) obtained from the PFAM website (<http://pfam.xfam.org/family/PF00067/hmm>). Cytochrome P450s were classified based on BLASTp searches (e-value < 1E-10) against the Dr. Nelson's database of curated fungal cytochrome P450s (<https://drnelson.uthsc.edu/P450seqs.dbs.html>). Cytochrome P450s with a BLASTp hit with more than 45% identity and at least 70% coverage were classified according to its top BLASTp hit. Protein sequences of the cytochrome P450 were aligned with MAFFT v7.475 (parameters: --maxiterate 1000 --localpair), and all positions in the alignment containing gaps were removed with trimAl v1.4.1. The trimmed alignment was then used to infer a tree with IQTREE v2.1.2 using ModelFinder to determine the best substitution model (best-fit model LG+R2) and to perform 1000 rapid bootstrap replicates (parameters: -m MFP -B 1000).

S2.6 Prediction and analysis of genes encoding candidate secreted effector proteins (CSEPs).

Secreted proteins were predicted with SignalP v5.0 (79) with parameter `-org euk`. Secreted proteins were

considered candidate effectors based on three lines of evidence: i) secreted proteins classified as effectors with EffectorP v2.0 (23); ii) secreted proteins shorter than 250 aa, with cysteine content of at least 2%, no glycosylphosphatidylinositol (GPI) anchor as determined with PredGPI (FP rate > 0.005) (80), and no transmembrane domain in the mature protein as determined with TMHMM v2.0 (81); iii) proteins with no homologs in Leotiomycetes, except Erysiphales, based on a BLASTp search (e-value < 1E-3) against 93 annotated genomes of Leotiomycetes available at NCBI on 2021-03-18 (Fig S10). All secreted proteins that satisfied any of these three lines of evidence were classified as candidate secreted effector proteins (CSEPs). CSEPs were subsequently queried with BLASTp (e-value < 1E-5) against the Pathogen Host Interaction (PHI) database v4.13 (82) to identify putative homologs.

The Y/F/WxC motif (83) was identified among the CSEPs by parsing a single-line fasta file containing mature CSEPs (i.e. signal peptide trimmed) using the Unix command `sed 's/[W|F|Y][A-Z]C//g'`, then searching for the presence of the pipe (“|”) character.

To examine the conservation of the CSEPs in other *E. necator* isolates, the CSEP-encoding genes were mapped to the genome of isolates branching, C-strain, e1-101, Iodi, and Ranch9 (4) using Liftoff v1.6.3 (84). CSEPs that failed to map with Liftoff were queried with exonerate v2.4.0 (85) with parameters `-m protein2genome --bestn 1 --showtargetgff yes` and mapped to the *E. necator* genomes.

A total of 22 secreted proteins contained a microbial RNase domain (cl00212) and were further classified as RNase-like proteins associated with haustoria (RALPHs) (86). Because e-values of identified microbial RNase domains in these 22 predicted RALPHs were high (i.e. 1E-4 - 1E-09), we reasoned that RALPH-like proteins without a predicted microbial RNase domain above the e-value threshold (i.e. 1E-3) could be present among the secreted proteins. To search for such RALPH-like proteins, the 22 predicted RALPH proteins with a conserved microbial RNase domain were queried with BLASTp against all predicted proteins of EnFRAME01. Matched proteins with e-value < 1E-5 and at least 40% aa identity were also considered RALPH-like proteins. By doing so, the total number of RALPH-like proteins increased from 22 to 38. These 38 RALPH-like proteins were aligned with MAFFT v7.455 (87) with parameters `--maxiterate 1000 --localpair`. The resulting 817 aa in size alignment was processed with trimAl (88) to remove sites containing 50% or more gaps, resulting in a trimmed alignment of 465 aa. The trimmed alignment was used to infer a phylogenetic tree with IQ-TREE v1.6.11 (89) using 1000 ultrafast bootstrap replicates (90) and the substitution model FLU+F+G4 selected with the built-in ModelFinder (91).

A total of 11 Egh16-like virulence factor proteins were identified based on the presence of the Egh16-like virulence factor conserved domain (PF11327). Differently from RALPH-like proteins, all proteins containing an Egh16-like virulence factor domain also contained a predicted signal peptide, and the e-values of the Egh16-like virulence factor domain were lower (between 3.3E-48 and 4.4E-67). Following the same approach described for RALPH-like proteins, a multiple sequence alignment of 499 aa was obtained

for the 11 Egh16-like virulence factor proteins. The alignment was trimmed, resulting in an alignment of 257 aa, that was used to infer a phylogenetic tree using the WAG+F+R2 substitution model.

S2.7 Identification of MACGs in *E. necator*. Protein sequences from EnFRAME01, *Blumeria graminis* f.sp. *hordei* isolate DH14 (https://fungi.ensembl.org/Blumeria_graminis/Info/Index), *Botrytis cinerea* isolate B05.10 (GCA_000143535.4), *Zymoseptoria tritici* isolate IPO323 (GCA_000219625.1), *Aspergillus niger* isolate CBS 513.88 (GCA_000002855.2), *Neurospora crassa* isolate OR74A (GCA_000182925.2), and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* isolate S288C (GCF_000146045.2) were organized into hierarchical orthogroups (HOGs) with OrthoFinder v2.5.4 (92) with parameters -t 8 -M msa -A mafft -T fasttree. HOGs containing protein sequences from non-obligate fungi analyzed, i.e. *B. cinerea*, *Z. tritici*, *A. niger*, *N. crassa*, and *S. cerevisiae*, but not from *E. necator* were considered as candidate MACGs in *E. necator*. These genes were further filtered based on enzyme commission (EC) numbers. First, all predicted proteins from EnFRAME01 were queried with BlastKOALA webserver (93) to obtain EC numbers. Then, corresponding EC numbers of the candidate MACGs in *E. necator* were obtained for the *S. cerevisiae* proteins by searching their accession numbers in the UniProt database (www.uniprot.org). If a gene from *E. necator* had an assigned EC number identical to an EC number of a MACG in *E. necator*, then this gene was no longer considered missing. Finally, a KEGG pathway enrichment analysis of the *E. necator* MACGs was performed with the YeastEnrichr webserver (<https://maayanlab.cloud/YeastEnrichr/>) (94), by using the corresponding *S. cerevisiae* gene names.

S2.8 Compartmentalization of the genome of *E. necator*. First, all intergenic regions were identified with the script complement from BEDtools v2.29.0, which obtained regions (i.e. intervals) of the genome not covered by genes. Then, up- and downstream intergenic regions were identified using the script closest from the BEDtools v2.29.0 software. The script was executed once to identify the downstream intergenic regions (parameters -t first -D a -iu), and then once more to identify the upstream intergenic regions (parameters -t first -D a -id). A heat map of the size of intergenic regions was obtained with the script geom_hex (parameter bins=50) from the R package ggplot2 v3.3.5 within R v4.1.2. Up- and downstream intergenic regions were grouped based on gene categories (i.e. BUSCOs, candidate effectors, secreted not candidate effectors, CAZymes, and proteases). Their sizes were compared, as well as their repetitive DNA content. To estimate their repetitive DNA content, the script coverage from BEDtools was used to calculate the percentage of the intergenic regions covered by repeats, using the repeat coordinates (GFF format) generated by RepeatMasker. Statistical significance was obtained with the Wilcoxon rank sum test implemented in the function wilcox.test within R v4.1.2.

S2.9 Classification, analysis, and enrichment of duplicated genes. An all-vs-all BLASTp search with parameters -max_hsps 5 -max_target_seqs 5 evaluate 1E-5 was performed to identify duplicated genes. To reduce the number of false positives, only BLASTp hits with identity values greater than 40% and at least 50% query and subject coverage were retained. The filtered output of BLASTp was used by the script

duplicate_gene_classifier from MCScanX (95) to classify gene duplications into dispersed, proximal, or tandem. Briefly, dispersed duplications corresponded to gene copies located in different chromosomes or with more than ten genes in between copies. Proximal duplications corresponded to gene copies with one to ten genes in between copies. Tandem duplications corresponded to gene copies with no genes in between copies. Conservation of dispersed, proximal, and tandem duplicated genes at the nucleotide (i.e. coding sequence) and amino acid levels were estimated by aligning each duplicate gene with its corresponding top BLASTp hit (not to itself). To do so, pairwise alignments were obtained with the pairwiseAlignment function (parameter: type = "global-local") from the Biostrings package v2.64.0 (96) within R v4.2.1. The "global-local" alignment strategy was used in which only the shortest of the two sequences is aligned end-to-end. Percent identity values of the alignments were obtained with the function pid (parameter: type = "PID1") from the Biostrings package. The "PID1" was used within pid in order to take into consideration internal gaps, but not gaps at both ends of the alignment. The top BLASTp hits were also used to estimate selection pressure of duplicated genes based on the K_A/K_S ratio (number of substitutions per nonsynonymous sites (K_A) per number of substitutions per synonymous sites (K_S)). To do so, the query and its top BLASTp hit were aligned with the Needleman-Wunsch global alignment algorithm (parameters -aformat fasta -gapopen 10 -gapextend 0.5) from EMBOSS v6.6.0. Amino acid alignments were converted to codon alignments with PAL2NAL v14. Codon alignments in FASTA format were then converted to AXT format and given as input to K_A/K_S _calculator v3 to estimate K_A/K_S ratios using the MA method. Conserved domain enrichment within duplicated genes was performed with the function enricher from the R package clusterProfiler v4.2.2 (97) within R v4.1.2 with parameters pvalueCutoff=0.01 pAdjustMethod="BH" qvalueCutoff=0.01 minGSSize=1. A dot plot of the significantly enriched domains was generated with the function dotplot from the enrichplot v 1.14.1 software. Statistical significance for different duplication frequencies of different gene categories was obtained with hypergeometric tests implemented in the phyper function within R v4.1.2. Statistical significance for different conservation levels and K_A/K_S ratios for dispersed, proximal, and tandem duplicated genes was obtained the Wilcoxon rank sum test implemented in the function wilcox.test within R v4.1.2.

S2.10 Organization of duplicated genes into orthogroups. To identify potential gene families expanded by gene duplications, all predicted protein sequences of EnFRAME01, C-strain (GCA_000798715.1), *Erysiphe pulchra* isolate Cflorida (GCA_002918395.1), *Golovinomyces cichoracearum* isolate UMSG1 (GCA_003611235.1), *Oidium neolycopersici* (GCA_003610855.1), *Blumeria graminis* f.sp. *hordei* isolate DH14 (https://fungi.ensembl.org/Blumeria_graminis/Info/Index), *B. graminis* f.sp. *tritici* isolate 96224 (GCA_900519115.1), and *Botrytis cinerea* isolate B05.10 (GCA_000143535.4) were organized into hierarchical orthogroups (HOGs) with OrthoFinder v2.5.4 (92) with parameters -t 12 -M msa -A mafft -T fasttree. The number of duplicated genes of EnFRAME01 within HOGs were counted. HOGs containing at least three duplicated genes of EnFRAME01 were considered candidate gene families

expanded by frequent gene duplications, and were further analyzed. Presence of secreted proteins, CSEPs, and conserved domains of proteins within these HOGs were reported.

S2.11 Identification of CNV genes. Whole-genome sequencing reads of *E. necator* isolates Branching (SRR1448453), C-strain (SRR1448450), e1-101 (SRR1448468), Lodi (SRR1448470), and Ranch9 (SRR1448454) (4) were obtained from the Sequence Read Archive (SRA). Reads were mapped to the genome of EnFRAME01 with BWA-MEM v0.7.17 (49). PCR duplicates were marked with samblaster v0.1.24 (50) and further removed with SAMtools v1.9 (51). Based on the resulting mapped reads, CNV regions were identified with CNVnator (98) using bin sizes of 150 bp for strain e1-101, 200 bp for strains branching and C-strain, and 300 bp for strains Lodi and Ranch9. Predicted CNV regions with a reported t-test e-value > 0.001 or with more than 50% reads mapped with mapping quality=0 were removed. Furthermore, only the CNV regions with normalized read depth < 0.2 (putative deletion) or normalized read depth > 1.8 (putative duplication) were retained. Genes that had at least 80% of their sequences overlapping CNV regions, as determined with the script overlap from BEDtools v2.29.0, were considered CNV genes (deleted or duplicated).

S2.12 Comparative analysis of carboxylesterases (CEs). The predicted carboxylesterase encoded by the gene *HI914_00624* was queried with BLASTp against the NCBI nr database (2022-08-13) and proteins from EnFRAME01. The 400 most similar sequences (e-value < 1E-50) were obtained to construct a phylogenetic tree. The acetylcholinesterase DmAChE from *Drosophila melanogaster* (1QO9), for which the 3D structure has been elucidated (99), was included as outgroup. The 401 amino acid sequences were then aligned with MAFFT v7.487 with parameters --maxiterate 1000 --localpair --thread 12, resulting in an alignment of 3442 aa. Sites containing 50% or more gaps were removed with trimAl, resulting in an alignment of 564 aa. The trimmed alignment was used to infer a phylogenetic tree with IQ-TREE v1.6.12 (89) using 1000 rapid bootstrap replicates (90) and the substitution model WAG+F+R10 selected by the built-in ModelFinder (91). The tree was visualized and edited with iTOL (100). Identification of conserved residues was performed by analyzing the residues from other sequences aligned to the conserved residues previously described in DmAChE (46, 99). Specifically, the catalytic triad Ser238, Glu367, and His480, the oxyanion hole residues Gly150, Gly151, and Ala239, the nucleophilic elbow formed by the pentapeptide Gly236, Glu237, Ser238, Ala239, and Gly240 (i.e., the GxSxG motif), and the six cysteine residues Cys66, Cys93, Cys292, Cys307, Cys442, and Cys560 that form three disulfide bridges in DmAChE (46, 99). A sequence logo was obtained with WebLogo (101) based on the trimmed alignment.

S2.13 Assessment of *HI914-00624* gene copy number and of its expression. Quantitative PCR (qPCR) and quantitative reverse transcription PCR (RT-qPCR) were used to determine the copy number and gene expression of the *HI914-00624* gene, respectively, using the single-copy *EnEF1* elongation factor 1 gene as reference in *E. necator* isolates EnFRAME01, C-strain, HO1, MEN8B, CAT1, and BL1-2. Conidia of the isolates were collected from the grapevine leaves 14 days after inoculation using the methods

described above. Genomic DNA was extracted from conidia using a rapid Chelex method (102) and total RNA was isolated using the methods described in S2.1. cDNA was generated using SuperScript IV Reverse Transcriptase (Invitrogen), using the provided random hexamers and following the manufacturer's protocol. All qPCR reactions were run in triplicate on an Applied Biosystems QuantStudio5 qPCR machine using PerfeCTa qPCR ToughMix Low ROX (Quantabio) and the primers and probes listed in [Table S26](#). The following cycling conditions were used: 95°C for 2 min followed by 45 cycles of 95°C for 15 sec and 62C for 45 sec. Gene copy number and expression were calculated using the $\Delta\Delta CT$ relative quantification method where $RQ = 2^{-\Delta\Delta CT}$. For these calculations, the *EnEF1* single-copy gene, whose expression was shown to be constant across inoculation time points (4), was treated as the control gene and EnFRAME01 was the reference isolate. *HI914-00624* PCR products were confirmed by Sanger sequencing.

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

FIG S1. Hi-C contact heatmap and diagram of the predicted chromosomes of *Erysiphe necator* isolate EnFRAME01. (A) The heat map represents the Hi-C contact matrix across the genome of EnFRAME01. High frequency interaction is shown in red scale. The figure shows the 11 predicted chromosomes as regions with high interaction frequency. Predicted centromeres of different chromosomes interact with each other. (B) Diagram of the 11 predicted chromosomes with predicted centromeric regions shown as white ellipses. Based on the ratio (r) of the estimated size of the long and short arms, the chromosomes were classified as metacentric ($1.0 < r < 1.7$), submetacentric ($1.7 < r < 3.0$), or subtelocentric ($3.0 < r < 7.0$), according to Levan et al. (1967).

FIG S2. The mitochondrial genomes of *Erysiphe necator* isolates EnFRAME01 and C-strain are highly conserved. The figure shows a dot plot of the alignment between the two mitochondrial genomes. A single aligned block with nucleotide identity of 99.7% covers the entire sequences of both mitochondrial genomes. The mitochondrial genome of C-strain was obtained from NCBI (NC_056146.1) and aligned to that of EnFRAME01 using NUCmer from the MUMmer software package v4.

FIG S3. Coverage of sequenced DNA-seq and RNA-seq reads across the 11 chromosomes of *Erysiphe necator* isolate EnFRAME01. (A) Heatmap showing the number of predicted protein coding genes. (B) Heatmap showing the percentage of repetitive DNA. (C) Coverage (0x to 200x) of the sequenced PacBio reads used to produce the assembly. (D) Coverage (0x to 200x) of whole-genome sequencing Illumina reads used to polish the assembly. (E) Coverage in log10 scale (0x to 10000x) of RNA-seq reads used to predict the protein coding genes. The five blue triangles indicate regions where PacBio and Illumina coverage exceeds twice the median for the entire genome, and indicates predicted collapsed regions in the assembly. Values in all tracks were determined using a sliding window of 50 kb.

FIG S4. The 11 chromosomes of *Erysiphe necator* are not syntenic to the chromosomes or scaffolds of the cereal powdery mildew pathogens *Blumeria graminis* f.sp. *tritici*, *B. graminis* f.sp. *triticales*, and *B. graminis* f.sp. *hordei*. Dot plot showing whole-genome alignments at the protein level of the 11 chromosomes of *E. necator* isolate EnFRAME01 and the 11 chromosomes of (A) *B. graminis* f.sp. *tritici* isolate v3.16, (B) the 11 chromosomes of *B. graminis* f.sp. *triticales* isolate THUN12, and (C) the 318 scaffolds of *B. graminis* f.sp. *hordei* isolate DH14. Protein alignments were obtained with PROmer. Predicted centromeres in the chromosomes of *E. necator* are highlighted with grey bars. The figure shows that the genome alignments are largely composed of non-syntenic regions and the predicted centromeric regions of *E. necator* are essentially unaligned. For *B. graminis* f.sp. *hordei* DH14, only the names of the 14 longest scaffolds are shown.

FIG S5: Genes encoding cytochrome P450s in the genome of *Erysiphe necator* isolate EnFRAME01. The figure shows an unrooted maximum likelihood (ML) phylogenetic tree of the cytochrome P450s. Classified P450s have their respective family name in bold next to the encoding gene IDs. Protein size and conserved PFAM domains within them are shown in scale on the right-hand side. All proteins contain a single P450 domain (PF00067). Gene *HI914_06959* encodes a cytochrome P450 with two additional domains corresponding to animal heme-dependent peroxidase (PF03098). The cytochrome P450 genes *HI914_05544*, *HI914_005519*, and *HI914_05505* are predicted paralogs because they share aa identity of more than 40%.

FIG S6: Genes encoding ATP-binding cassette (ABC) transporters in the genome of *Erysiphe necator* isolate EnFRAME01. The figure shows a maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree of the ABC transporters. The domain architectures of the ABC transporters are shown in scale on the right-hand side and include the conserved ATP-binding domain (PF00005) and transmembrane domains. Classification of the ABC transporters into classes ABCC, ABCB, ABCG, ABCE, ABCD, ABCF, and ABCI is shown on the far right-hand side.

FIG S7. Venn diagram of candidate secreted effector proteins (CSEPs) from *Erysiphe necator* isolate EnFRAME01 that are species-specific or shared with other fungi. CSEPs of EnFRAME01 were considered as shared as if they had BLASTp hits ($e\text{-value} < 1E\text{-}5$) to predicted proteins from the dicot-infecting powdery mildews (PM) *Erysiphe pulchra* isolate Cflorida, *Erysiphe neolycopersici* isolate UMSG2, *Golovinomyces cichoracearum* isolate UMSG3, *Golovinomyces cichoracearum* isolate UCSC1, *Golovinomyces cichoracearum* isolate UMSG1, *Golovinomyces magnicellulatus* isolate FPH2017-1, and *Podosphaera aphanis* isolate DRCT72020, the monocot-infecting PMs *Blumeria graminis* f.sp. *hordei* isolate RACE1, *Blumeria graminis* f.sp. *hordei* isolate DH14, *Blumeria graminis* f.sp. *tritici* isolate v3.16, *Blumeria graminis* f.sp. *tritici* isolate 96224, and *Blumeria graminis* f.sp. *triticales* isolate THUN12, or other fungi in the NCBI nr database.

FIG S8. Histograms of Y/F/W-x-C motifs in candidate secreted effector proteins (CSEPs) of *Erysiphe necator* isolate EnFRAME01. The histograms show the number of Y/F/W-x-C motifs located in different regions of mature CSEPs (i.e. after signal peptide cleavage). In the histograms, 0% represents the N-terminus, and 100% represents the C-terminus. Preference of Y/F/W-x-C motifs located near the N-terminus can be observed.

FIG S9. *Erysiphe necator* isolate EnFRAME01 has two major clades of predicted genes encoding RNase-like proteins associated with haustoria (RALPHs). Maximum likelihood (ML) phylogenetic tree of the 38 RALPH-like proteins identified in EnFRAME01. Ultrafast bootstrap support is shown on branches. Protein size, presence of a signal peptide, and location of microbial ribonuclease (RNase) domains (cl00212) are shown next to the encoding gene labels. RALPH-like proteins further classified as candidate secreted effector proteins (CSEPs) are indicated with an asterisk (*). The locations on the chromosomes of EnFRAME01 of the genes encoding RALPH-like proteins are shown with hollow triangles connected with lines. The figure shows that genes encoding RALPH-like proteins are organized into two major clades (clade A and B) based on their similarity, size of encoded proteins, and their location on the chromosomes.

FIG S10. *Erysiphe necator* isolate EnFRAME01 has two major groups of predicted genes encoding Egh16-like proteins. Maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree of the Egh16-like proteins present in EnFRAME01. Ultrafast bootstrap support is shown on the branches. Egh16-like proteins further classified as candidate secreted effector proteins (CSEPs) are indicated with an asterisk (*). Protein size, presence of a signal peptide, and location of Egh16-like virulence factor domains (PF11327) are shown next to the encoding gene labels. The heatmap shows the percent amino acid identity values obtained with BLASTp by querying the candidate effectors gEgh16 (JC4750) and Egh16H1 (CCU76428.1) from *Blumeria graminis* f.sp. *hordei*. The locations on the chromosomes of EnFRAME01 of the genes encoding the Egh16-like proteins is shown with hollow triangles connected with lines. The figure shows that genes encoding Egh16-like proteins are organized into two major clades (clade A and B) based on their similarity and location in the chromosomes.

FIG S11. The genome of *Erysiphe necator* has a different transposable element (TE) content compared to the genomes of cereal powdery mildews (PMs). The bar plots represent the repetitive DNA landscape of *E. necator* isolate EnFRAME01, *Blumeria graminis* f.sp. *hordei* isolate DH14, *Blumeria graminis* f.sp. *tritici* isolate v3.16, and *Blumeria graminis* f.sp. *triticales* isolate THUN12. The repetitive DNA landscape for each pathogen was obtained by masking its genome, using its respective custom *de novo* repetitive DNA library. Percentages shown at the top right corner of each plot indicate the amount of masked bases in the genome. The figure shows that, when using TE libraries of the cereal PMs, almost all TEs with low sequence divergence are not identified in the genome of *E. necator*. Similarly, when using the TE library of *E. necator*, almost all TEs with low sequence divergence are not identified in the genomes of the cereal PMs.

FIG S12. The chromosomes of *Erysiphe necator* isolate EnFRAME01 exhibit negative correlation between gene density and repetitive DNA content. Scatter plot showing the number of genes per Mb and repetitive DNA content of the chromosomes. The regression line is shown in blue and was determined with the `geom_smooth` function from the R package `ggplot2`, utilizing the “`lm`” method. Dark areas represent confidence intervals (95%). Correlation coefficient and p -value of the regression line are shown at the top right corner.

FIG S13. The genome of *Erysiphe necator* isolate EnFRAME01 exhibits no major differences in predicted transposable element (TE) content in intergenic regions of selected functional gene categories. The bar plots show the percentage of the different TE (super)families (A) upstream and (B) downstream of intergenic regions of predicted BUSCO genes, carbohydrate-active enzymes (CAZymes), proteases, secreted proteins not classified as candidate secreted effector proteins (CSEP), and CSEPs.

FIG S14. Genes encoding secreted proteins and candidate secreted effector proteins (CSEPs) are expanded by frequent local duplications in *Erysiphe necator* isolate EnFRAME01. The bar plot shows the number of duplicated genes organized in 88 hierarchical orthogroups (HOGs). Duplicated gene copies are classified into dispersed, proximal, or tandem. HOGs that contain at least one gene encoding a secreted protein or a CSEP are indicated with rectangles below the bars. HOGs are assigned to a conserved domain if this domain is present in at least one of the proteins in the respective HOG. The figure shows that duplicated genes encoding secreted proteins and CSEPs are preferentially organized into HOGs that include genes locally duplicated.

FIG S15. The chromosome 1 (Chr1) of *Erysiphe necator* isolate EnFRAME01 harbors a genomic region that contains 20 copies of a gene encoding a candidate secreted effector protein (CSEP). (A) The figure shows a 350 kb zoomed-in region in chromosome 1 containing 20 copies of a CSEP. Genes within the locus are represented as black rectangles and the CSEP copies indicated with triangles. The dot plot shows the locus aligned to itself, with repetitive regions shown as dots not on the main diagonal. (B) Multiple sequence alignment of the 20 CSEP copies. All 20 copies have the same DNA strand orientation and all were confirmed to be absent of introns based on RNA-seq data. Copies 3 to 17 encode identical proteins.

FIG S16. Local gene duplicates in the genome of *Erysiphe necator* isolate EnFRAME01 are likely younger in age, and exhibit more relaxed selection pressure than dispersed gene duplicates. (A) Box-plots showing the distribution values of synonymous substitutions per synonymous site (K_S), non-synonymous substitutions per non-synonymous site (K_A), and of the K_A/K_S ratio, calculated for pairs of gene duplicates in the genome of EnFRAME01. Proximal gene duplicates (PGDs) and tandem gene duplicates (TGDs) have lower median K_S values as compared to the dispersed gene duplicates (DGDs), which further experience a bimodal distribution with peaks at $K_S \approx 3-3.5$ and $K_S \approx 0.05$ in the distribution of K_S values. Moreover, PGDs and TGDs exhibit higher median K_A/K_S values that are closer to 1 as compared to DGDs, indicating more relaxed selection pressure. (B) The distributions of K_S (left panel) and nucleotide identity values (right panel) of duplicated genes in the genome of EnFRAME01 do not exhibit an L-shaped pattern as secondary peaks are observed at the tail of the two distributions. K_S and amino-acid identity values were calculated based on pairwise comparisons of each duplicated gene with its most homologous paralog. (C) Duplicated genes encoding candidate secreted effector proteins (CSEPs) are likely of younger age, and under more relaxed selection pressure as compared to other functional gene categories in the genome of EnFRAME01. The box-plots show the distribution of K_S , K_A , and K_A/K_S values calculated for pairs of gene duplicates organized into different gene functional categories.

FIG S17. Copy number variation (CNV) regions in the genome of *Erysiphe necator* isolate EnFRAME01 differ in size, repeat content, and are less frequently observed in gene-rich regions. (A) Size distribution of CNV regions. Each point corresponds to a CNV region. (B) Box plots showing the overall number of CNV regions within centromeric regions, gene-rich regions, repeat-rich regions, and subtelomeric regions. Each point corresponds to a 50 kb window containing the number of CNVs shown in the Y-axis. There is a total of 257 windows from centromeric regions, 144 windows from gene-rich regions (i.e. 50 kb windows containing at least 10 predicted genes), 230 windows from repeat-rich regions (i.e. 50 kb windows containing at least 90% repeats), and 220 windows from subtelomeric regions (i.e. within 500 kb from chromosome ends). (C) Bar plots showing the percentage of transposable element (TE) content within CNV regions compared to the entire genome. *P*-values are of Wilcoxon rank sum tests.

FIG S18. Distribution of copy number variation (CNV) regions in the chromosomes of *Erysiphe necator* isolate EnFRAME01. Tracks (A) and (B) show histograms of the number of deletions and duplications, respectively. Track (C) shows the number of predicted genes in grey scale. Track (D) shows the location of duplications and deletions with rectangles in the upper and lower halves of the track, respectively. Location of protein encoding genes affected by duplications and deletions are indicated with upside down and upright triangles, respectively. Values shown in the tracks (A), (B), and (C) were obtained using a sliding window of 50 kb. CNV regions shown were obtained by merging overlapping CNV regions identified by analyzing the *E. necator* isolates C-strain, e1-101, Lodi, Branching, and Ranch9.

FIG S19. The relative expression of the *HI914_00624* gene encoding a secreted carboxylesterase (CE) is strongly correlated to its copy numbers. The scatter plot shows the linear relationship between *HI914-00624* copy number (X-axis) as determined by qPCR in six old isolates of *E. necator* (i.e. EnFRAME01, CAT1, BL1-2, HO1, MEN8B, and C-strain) and *HI914-00624* expression (Y-axis) as determined by RT-qPCR in conidia of the isolates harvested from detached *Vitis vinifera* L., cv. 'Chardonnay' leaves at 2-weeks post inoculation. Both qPCR assays used the single-copy *EnEF1* (*E. necator* elongation factor 1) gene as reference and EnFRAME01 as the reference isolate. Relative gene expression calculated using the $\Delta\Delta\text{CT}$ method where $\text{RQ} = 2^{-\Delta\Delta\text{CT}}$.

FIG S20. The secreted carboxylesterase (CE) encoded by the HI914_00624 gene in *Erysiphe necator* isolate EnFRAME01 as well as its homologs in powdery mildew genomes (PM) are likely catalytically inactive. The figure shows an amino-acid alignment of HI914_00624, its homologs in other PM genomes, and the acetylcholinesterase DmAChE from *Drosophila melanogaster* (1Q09), for which the 3D structure has been elucidated. The sequence logo (max = log₂0 = 4.3 bits) was inferred from the trimmed alignment of HI914_00624 and 400 most similar sequences found in GenBank, together with DmAChE as an outgroup (Fig 5C). Sites with at least 80% identity or similarity among the 23 sequences shown are highlighted. Conserved residues in DmAChE are indicated as reported by Oakeshott et al. (46). The figure shows that HI914_00624 and its homologs in PM genomes do not have the conserved Ser (S238) and His (H480) residues of the catalytic triad Ser-Asp/Glu-His required for the proper function of CEs. The PM species of each sequence is shown in Table S23.

FIG S21. Workflow used to identify candidate secreted effector proteins (CSEPs) in *Erysiphe necator* isolate EnFRAME01. CSEPs were identified based on three lines of evidence: i) secreted proteins with no transmembrane domain and no glycosylphosphatidylinositol (GPI) anchor with no homologs in non-powdery mildew Leotiomyces, ii) secreted proteins with no transmembrane domain and no GPI anchor with at most 250 aa and at least 2% cysteine residues, and iii) secreted proteins classified as effector by EffectorP. The number of CSEPs identified by each of these three lines of evidence are indicated on the right-hand side.

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